

WP3 – Accounting for agroforestry benefits: tools for beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services

Schematic Maps of the Agroforestry Value Chain for each Living Lab

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1 Context - The DigitAF project

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 to June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Participatory research approach is key to engaging with actors involved in the development of agroforestry and to unlock synergies among stakeholders and other research to facilitate the implementation of innovations. An overall objective of the project is to provide three groups of stakeholders with digital tools that address their needs and expectation. The three groups of stakeholders addressed by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry systems and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of agroforestry systems, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of agroforestry in clear and accessible terms.

2 Introduction

In this preliminary action of the project, our goal is to identify the actors and flow of products and services both upstream and downstream from by the participatory analysis of value chain constraints for developing novel diversification systems.

This report introduces and presents the work conducted to develop the multi-stakeholder action aimed at identifying the principal functions, actors, and supports in the agroforestry (AF) value chain and the principal flows of products, services, information, and finance.

The deliverable forms part of DigitAF work-package (WP) 3, which deals with the use of digital tools and methods to improve the accounting of agroforestry benefits and costs within value chains. In order to improve our understanding of the value chains related to agroforestry, we developed a method to derive a schematic map of the agroforestry value chain at each of Living Lab (LL) involved in the project and a Spanish case study.

3 Methodology

3.1 Selection of case studies

The preparation of the schematic maps of value chains related to agroforestry were focused on the six DigitAF living labs situated in Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, Finland, Czechia, and the United Kingdom (Figure 1). In addition, as outlined in the original DigitAF application, we also included a case study from Spain that considers the use of blockchain in the beef sector.

Figure 1. Map showing location and spread of the Living Labs within Europe. The orange pins indicate central location to each of the Living Labs

3.2 Research protocol for the value mapping activities

A research protocol was developed ahead of the value chain mapping to ensure that each living lab partners could facilitate the mapping in a participatory manner and in order to produce comparable results (Appendix A). However, the diversity and the heterogeneity of the living labs and the connected value chains meant that in practice, the proposed methodology was slightly changed and adapted to the specific situation.

The protocol comprised five sections.

3.2.1 Behaviours of the facilitator

In ensuring effective and enjoyable workshops is critical. Guidance on the role of the facilitator is also provided in Appendix A, together with guidance on planned behaviours and activities.

3.2.2 Ice breaking activities

If the group had not met before, the protocol proposed a series of ice breaking activities. The objective of this activity was to help the participants comfortable enough to provide input and participate actively.

3.2.3 “Speed dating” session on current needs and future expectations

The next proposed activity (which was optional depending on the circumstance) was to arrange a “speed dating” session to encourage participants of the living lab to know each other further, by speaking to each other for 3 to 5 minutes. Within the activity, participants were asked to complete a “Needs and Expectations” form. Full details are given in Appendix A. “Needs” were specified as current short-term issues or necessities with the other stakeholders, while “expectations” were related to something related to the future.

3.2.4 Value chain mapping

According to the literature, a value chain describes “the full range of activities which are required to bring a product or service from conception, through the different phases of production (involving a combination of physical transformation and input of various producer services), delivery to final consumers, and final disposal after use” (Kaplinsky and Morris, 2000).

Across each living lab, a participatory modeling approach was used to produce a schematic overview of the value chain. The approach used was a concept mapping methodology, which is a qualitative modelling type that allows conceptualization (Voinov et al., 2018). Concept maps are graphical representations of organized knowledge that visually illustrate the relationships among elements within a knowledge domain. The objective of the activity was not to produce an accurate estimation of costs and monetary flows or life cycle costing analysis, but to capture stakeholder perceptions of the main goods and services in the value chains. Obviously, this requires some simplification and assumptions, and it was expected that stakeholders would give priority to the products or services regarded most important by them. Two aspects that can be helpful to include in the analysis are the system boundaries (represented graphically), and the primary “functional units”, which are likely to be products or services such as, for example, cereal crops and carbon storage.

A possible procedure, based on work by Stein and Barron (2017), is presented in Appendix A. That procedure suggests that individual stakeholders use sticky notes to describe specific actors in the value chain which are then placed on a map. Then, once the main actors are identified, the linkages connecting the various actors are drawn. In general, many flows of products are associated with flows of money going in the other direction; however, there can also be flows of information and sharing of technical knowledge. Where possible different links such as information or money were drawn with different coloured pens.

3.2.5 Analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats

Selected living labs also completed a “SWOT” analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in order to identify upgrading opportunities at the various nodes of the value chain. This was either done through facilitated discussion or through the completion of a form (See Appendix A).

3.3 Analysis of results

After the exercise, the results of each value chain mapping activity were translated into English and collated by staff at the University of Pisa. During the analysis a map of each value chain was created using MindMaple software (<https://www.mindmaple.com>).

4 Results: Italy

4.1 Description of the Italian living lab

The Italian living lab comprised four farmers (one farmer/entrepreneur, two livestock farmers, and one olive producer), four consultants, and three participants (one value chain actor/seller, one representative of certification company, and one vet) in the value chain. The primary agricultural product of interest is beef. The mapping activity was conducted between 30 and 31 May 2023 (Figure 2).

Some of the members of the Living Lab already knew each other while some of them met for the first time. An ice breaking activity was conducted to make the atmosphere more familiar and help the participants to learn something more about each other.

Figure 2. Photograph of participants and researchers taken during workshop

4.2 Needs and expectations

When farmers met with farmers, they highlighted the need to manage different production systems within agroforestry system, the need for knowledge exchange and networking, and the need to improve the value of local breeds. The expectations included increased quality of production, the benefits of working together to protect the environment, and possibly increased tourism (Table 1).

When farmers met with consultants the identified needs included collaboration. There was also an interest in ways to improve soil health without compromising meat production. Consultants were interested to know more about the critical issues for farmers. In the discussions between farmers and a representative of a certification company there was a perceived need for farmers to understand if certification was useful to the farm, whilst the representative expected to maintain the credibility of the certification. In the farmer-researcher and farm-value chain interactions, the farmers emphasised the need for data and scientific evidence that was of practical use, and the researchers and value chain actors were interested in the critical challenges on farms. There was an expectation of long-term collaboration. In the discussion between the farmers and the vet, the expressed needs were a focus on prevention rather than cure of diseases and an expectation that more work was

needed on the integration of animals with different production systems, including an assessment of the risks from wild animals (Table 1).

Table 1. Current needs and future expectations of the farmers between themselves and with different groups

	Current needs	Future expectations
Farmer with farmer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Learn management of different productions, integrating them (i.e. olive groves, livestock productions) adding new products in the value chain ○ Knowledge exchange, learning new production systems (i.e. organic) ○ Networking to protect the territory ○ Valorisation of autochthonous breeds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase quality of productions and integration of productive systems ● Collaboration and networking to create projects that protect the agroecosystem ● Increase tourism linked to livestock management
Farmer with consultant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Collaboration and synergy ○ Consultants need to clearly know farmers objectives and critical points ○ Increase productions ○ Agronomic solutions to increase soil health without compromising animal productivity ○ Innovative agricultural farms ○ Access to knowledge and experiences ○ Long-term collaboration to achieve results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Stable productions in long term to increase farmers income ○ Collaboration in the long-term ○ Create collaboration with other farms through consultants
Farmer with certification company	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Farmers need to understand how the certification scheme works understanding if it is valuable for the farm ○ How a possible agroforestry system can work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Do not lose credibility of the certification ○ Certification of a product in an AF system
Farmer with researcher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Farmers need data and scientific evidence to understand if the process works, scientific work must have practical advantages for the farm ○ Researcher needs to understand the critical points of the livestock farm obtaining real data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Long-term collaboration
Farmer with value chain actor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Farmers need data and scientific evidence to understand if the process works, scientific work must have practical advantages for the farm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Long-term collaboration, customer education
Farmer with vet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Working on prevention rather than the cure ○ Management plan including animals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Integration of different production, i.e. with animals ○ Evaluation of risks associated with wild animals

Within the discussions between non-farmers, the consultants when together identified the need to share strategies and to understand the requirements for agroforestry certification. There was a desire to create a network between consultants and to have a clearer understanding of innovations in relation to agroforestry, of agroforestry costs, and of options for EU funding (Table 2).

Table 2. Current needs and future expectations of non-farmers with different groups

	Current needs	Future expectations
Consultant with consultant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing of strategies • Need to know obligations and requirements to apply an agroforestry certification • Technology on how to certify farm with a circular economy, i.e. agroforestry farms • Collaborations for projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of long-term projects • Create a network between consultants sharing common strategies • Knowledge of costs linked to the production, inserting them into the business plan • Knowledge regarding the possibility to have access to EU funding • Sensibilization of all the consultants on innovative strategies
Consultant with certification company	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to know obligations and requirements to apply an agroforestry certification • Technology on how to certify farm with a circular economy, i.e. agroforestry farms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid losing the credibility of the certification • Create a network, favourable channel to find new clients for AF products
Consultant with value chain actor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the communication between actors • Push farmers to collaborate between them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovations in the practice and increase economic viability in the long term
Consultant with vet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding problems of animal reared in agroforestry systems • Share knowledge between different competences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with different technicians • Creation of a development plan with a focus on the economics aspects
Consultant with researcher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of past experiences and species used in the system • Research needs to be applicable to the farm • Researchers need the consultants to work as a bridge between them and the farmers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a network to develop projects at large scale
Researcher with value chain actor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The seller needs support the dissemination activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers need to know how to bring research into practice • Sellers needs instruments to earn from positive aspects of agriculture
Value chain actor with vet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardization of farm management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links with the farm through people

4.3 Schematic representation of the value chain

Because of the presence of a diverse group of stakeholders with different roles and positions in the workshop, the value chain built was complicated with several connections and points of view. The digitalized map (Figure 4) was slightly simplified compared to the physical value chain created by the farmers. To better represent the value chain, a legend with the following colours was used

Figure 3. Legend to be used for transcribing the value chain mapping exercise into digital form

The central agroforestry system considered was an agrosilvopastoral system. The products from the agroforestry system included meat, honey, timber and mushrooms, and other ecosystem services included climate change mitigation and landscape management. However, despite the wide range of services and products, the schematic diagram of the value chain focused on meat production (Figure 4).

4.4 Challenges and opportunities

Using Figure 4 as a basis of discussion, the participants identified many and different aspects of the value chain, with a tendency to focus more on challenges rather than opportunities.

Challenges: amongst the challenges identified were the that although there are measurements that help farmers, it is difficult to apply them. Knowledge gaps in terms of policy, excessive bureaucracy, and conflicts with environmentalists were also identified as constraints. The distinction between utilisable agricultural areas (Italian: Superficie Agricola Utilizzata (SAU)) and forests and the fact that forests do not receive payment from the Rural Development Programmes was also identified as a constraint for agroforestry. Authorisation of fences and forest grazing were also highlighted as constraints.

Other aspects discussed were:

Agricultural advice: there were different points of view as to whether farmers should pay for advisors or should corporations/government offer free assistance to the farmer. However, it was noted that sometimes, farmers do not trust free advisors.

Consortiums: a strong consortium (i.e. Parmigiano Reggiano) can provide a great opportunity to guarantee income for farmers but currently in Italy there are difficulties as they are missing.

Digital tools: it was thought that blockchain could be useful when data collection is automatic. However management software was not present on the farm at present.

Communication: limits of communication between research and farmers were identified, and it was felt important that there was a need to positively communicate farm activities to consumer.

Figure 4. Value chain map of Italian agroforestry products

Three other areas of discussion were:

Lobbying ability: the agricultural lobby was considered to have low power compared to other lobbies. Often there is disagreement between lobbies

Research: it was felt that research was not harmonized, with difficulties to communicate between different sectors. The “third mission” of universities was limited

Large carnivores: the increased presence of large carnivores were having a great impact on the farmers. There were difficulties in controlling the animals in an extensive environment/agroforestry system because of the risks, with consequences for management and animal welfare.

4.5 Reflections on the process

The discussion started in the afternoon of 30 May 2023 after the ice-breaking session and a presentation of the DIGITAF project with its objectives and goals.

The first general discussion was used to make participants more involved and confident with the environment, and covered the following topics/points:

Payment of positive externalities provided by agricultural farms: the non-agricultural entrepreneur insisted on the need to make this aspect profitable for the farm. In his vision this was the only way to make extensive farm economically viable.

Greenwashing activities and incorporating benefits: there was an explanation of insetting and offsetting and agroforestry seen as a real strategy of insetting.

Society perception of agricultural products: there were societal concerns about the environmental impact of beef. Stakeholder involved in the beef sector has a different view of the emissions generated by the sector. It was felt that there was a need to educate the consumers on food choices seeking to enhance the value of the product and justify the higher costs of production faced by extensive and small farms.

Organic and agroforestry certification schemes: it was considered that a long time was needed to create a certification scheme for agroforestry systems, particularly to assess the higher benefits. There was a discussion on whether certifying agroforestry is better than other production strategies, for example organic. For example, the PEFC certification took 20 years to be recognized. There was also some criticisms of organic certification because of the great exception

Future direction of the Common Agricultural Policy: it was perceived that the CAP tends to increase the level of biodiversity in the landscape with a land sharing approach. Farmers indicated that this approach made it more difficult to manage on their land but it was fit for the future. Farmers also saw the need for farms to stop being dependent from EU funding, they need to create a business plan based on their resources and not change their plan based on funding schemes. Regarding agroforestry funding, farmers highlighted the need to allow also for maintenance.

Difficulties of extensive farms to create economies of scale: because of the greater standardization of intensive farms they are able to create scale economies that guarantee certain profits. The participants cited the example of extra virgin oil exported to the United States.

5 Results: The Netherlands

5.1 Description of the Dutch living lab

The Dutch living lab comprised eight practitioners (six farmers and two advisers), six policy actors and two value chain actors from all parts of the Netherlands, representing the agroforestry sector in the Netherlands.

The range of agricultural services and products of agroforestry systems in The Netherlands is wide. Moreover, agroforestry systems are immature and not in full production. In this study, the Dutch group focused on the value chain of dairy farmers and in particular value chain of walnuts.

The initial mapping of the value chain was conducted on 7 June 2023. In November 2023, the map was refined by consulting a farmer, researchers in dairy farming systems, and a value chain expert.

5.2 Needs and expectations

Context: overall, agroforestry in The Netherlands is a very recent development. The earliest adopters of agroforestry in The Netherlands were livestock farmers. Around 2008, a small group of poultry farmers started to experiment with planting trees in their free-range areas. Parallel to poultry farmers, dairy farmers started to get interested in planting trees and shrubs for biomass, biodiversity, and animal welfare. Recently, the practice of fodder trees was adopted by a larger group of dairy farmers. Also, silvopastoral systems with standard fruit trees, walnut trees and hazelnut shrubs increased in popularity over the years. Dairy farmers now form the dominant group of agroforestry practitioners.

Starting from 2018, dairy farmers started agroforestry systems on a scale that surpasses 1 hectare. A large part of these systems was struck by the drought that followed the following two years. Only in the last 3-4 years systems over 5 hectares were implemented. In the past 2 years, a small group of arable farmers started to show interest in agroforestry and a handful started alley cropping systems. It can be stated that the number of farmers involved in agroforestry is in the hundreds. These farmers either recently started their agroforestry system or are in an advanced stage of their plans to realize agroforestry. Most of this group (estimated over 95%) planted trees in the last 5 years. Therefore, the value chain of agroforestry products is not yet developed. However, the importance of setting up value chains for agroforestry products is stressed by all parties involved in the Living Lab.

There are a few initiatives in The Netherlands that focus on setting up value chains for agroforestry products. The following needs and expectations were identified for the most important actors that are involved in these processes.

Farmers: an important argument for farmers not to start agroforestry is the lack of an existing value chain. In most cases the conventional farms have a limited number of agricultural products, that often end up being sold to one or two processors that offer long-term contracts. It is foreseen that adding additional agricultural products will result in the following needs.

- Information on customer demand for the next 20 years and which of the products can be produced in agroforestry systems.
- Information on what quality requirements the products have to meet.

- Instructions on what type of on-farm processing is needed to increase the value of the product (e.g. cleaning, drying, peeling).
- Insight into the minimal quantities that buyers need.
- Long-term agreements with off-takers and insight into the risks and challenges involved in the process.
- Enough (quantity) high quality trees to plant, suitable for agroforestry systems.
- Advice on the management of trees, agroforestry systems and setting up new revenue models.

Agroforestry consultants and advisors: many farm advisors in the Netherlands are not aware of agroforestry and they typically specialize in the financial aspects of production such as livestock care, crop production, and soil quality. However, despite the above specialized agroforestry consultants are becoming more common. For example, agroforestry farmers often connect with provincial agroforestry networks that provide agroforestry advisors. The most pressing needs of these advisors in the value chain are:

- Interesting example farms to learn from and visits with other farmers,
- Recent insights on designing agroforestry systems,
- Recent insights in agroforestry practices and agronomic solutions, such as planting, weeding, pruning, harvesting, and
- Contacts with farmers that are interested in applying agroforestry.

Farm suppliers: in general, the established farm suppliers in The Netherlands are not aware of the development of agroforestry, and those who are aware see agroforestry as a market too small to make profits. Therefore, farmers cannot turn to their regular contacts for advice on their agroforestry supplies. In the first years, the pioneering farmers spent much time finding the right supplies. However, recently, small supply companies have started to specialise in agroforestry products e.g. tree nurseries that grow trees specially for agroforestry systems. Some also include the supply of irrigation systems and tree protection. The needs of these actors include:

- Contact with farmers that are interested in implementing agroforestry,
- Information on the needs of farmers, especially what trees are in demand, to keep meeting the demand, since it takes several years to grow a tree before it can be planted in an agroforestry system.

Consumers: consumers were not a part of the Living Lab. However, in the value chain (of agroforestry products), the consumer plays a vital role. To be able to set up a sustainable value chain it is vital that consumers are more aware of agroforestry and can access agroforestry products easier. It is perceived that consumer needs in the agroforestry value chains are:

- General information on what agroforestry is and to what extent it is more sustainable than conventional agriculture,
- Access to reasonable priced agroforestry products.

Buyers: the buyer of the agroforestry product can be the end-consumer. It is expected that this is the case in most small-scale agroforestry systems. However, to apply agroforestry on a scale that contributes significantly to sustainability, it will also be necessary to upscale and develop a chain that takes care of the processing, packaging, storage and distribution of agroforestry products. These

buyers need to adapt their activities to cope with the processing of agroforestry products and, for example, need to purchase or adapt machinery. The needs of these buyers towards a value chain are:

- Reliable streams of agroforestry products (quantity) and (long-term) agreements with farmers,
- Insight in what agroforestry products to expect in the coming 5-10 years,
- Agroforestry products of quality. The demand for quality is different for each end-product. For eating apples taste and appearance are important and to produce walnut oil taste and oil content are what counts.
- Insight into what agroforestry is and to what extent and in what terms is it more sustainable than conventional agriculture, to market the product.

Buyers also include the parties to which the farmer sells their regular (non-agroforestry) products, such as meat, milk, cereals, and vegetables. These parties can benefit from the success of agroforestry and advertise that their products are manufactured at farms that apply agroforestry and have thus made their production process more sustainable in various aspects. These conventional buyers need to be more aware of agroforestry and need insight into what extent agroforestry is more sustainable on the topics of animal welfare, soil quality, biodiversity, and environmental aspects.

5.3 Schematic representation of the Dutch dairy value chain

Mapping the general value chain of agroforestry in The Netherlands based upon the findings above was proved to be very difficult because of the variety of farming systems and farming contexts. Therefore, it was suggested to map the value chain of a popular agroforestry system in The Netherlands. The following analyses focuses on a silvopastoral system with dairy cows and walnut production (Figure 5). The milk was sold to a milk factory and the nuts would be sold to a nut purchaser. It was also identified that the agroforestry system could offer benefits in terms of carbon sequestration and the provision of additional ecosystem services could mean that the agroforestry system would be eligible for agri-environmental support.

5.4 Challenges and opportunities

The challenges for selected actors in the value chain are described in the previous paragraphs. Hence this final section focused on the challenges and opportunities for the walnut chain at livestock farms.

Challenges: the identified challenges included:

- Most farmers involved in walnut production have only planted in recent years, so there is not yet enough production to set up solid value chains.
- In addition: although walnuts are among the most popular agroforestry products in The Netherlands, relatively few farmers are involved in silvopastoral agroforestry systems with walnuts. Agroforestry farmers with walnut production are distributed relatively far apart, making it difficult to form collectives and enthuse value chain partners.
- Potential buyers are hesitant about the quality of nuts that come from agroforestry systems because production is handled less 'professionally' than regular nut cultivation. For example, much less attention is paid to preventing pests and thus damage to the product.

Figure 5. Value chain of silvopastoral system with dairy cows and walnut production

- Walnuts of many different varieties have been planted, with different nut quality and uses. For the farmer, this requires a lot of knowledge of what management each species needs. Even more importantly, this causes major problems with sales. Different nut cultivars ripen at different times of the year and are of varying quality, which makes processing and marketing very difficult. Professionalization is needed in all areas.
- Buyers as well as farmers themselves question how a Dutch walnut can compete in price with a walnut that is produced in a region where agricultural land is not as expensive and regulation is not as strict as in the Netherlands.

Opportunities: the following opportunities were identified:

- In recent years, a small number of initiatives have been started that deal with the valorization of walnuts (in agroforestry systems). Walnut is the first agroforestry product where farmers are starting farming cooperatives to process and sell produce.
- The Nut Association in the Netherlands is very active and offers support and information on the topic of professionalization of cultivation and setting up revenue models.
- The purchasing policy of large organizations is increasingly focused on local and sustainable produced products. These large organizations also include local governments and nursing homes, for example, which means that large quantities are sold immediately.
- To seriously up-scale the value chain with large processors, the requirements and wishes of such parties must first be identified. The first steps of this process are already being taken.
- The sale of wood from walnut trees also has a lot of potential. Because these revenues are in the distant future, little attention has been paid to them yet.
- Within research projects, the emphasis is increasingly on the revenue model of agroforestry, particularly the PPP project Agroforestry Revenue Models project. From this project, a Community of Practice Revenue Models has been set up with the support of the Agroforestry Network Netherlands, in which approximately 25 professionals from different expertise worked on revenue models for agroforestry.
- The Dutch dairy sector is under considerable pressure due to, to mention a couple, due to nitrogen and biodiversity problems. In addition, in the Netherlands the largest share of agricultural land is used by dairy farmers, which means that dairy farmers are also encouraged to take steps towards more carbon sequestration and climate adaptation of agricultural landscapes. The dairy value chain could therefore benefit greatly from the development of agroforestry. More and more attention is being paid to this.

Suggestions for tools: a first exploration on the demand of tools to improve the value chain resulted in the following ideas:

- Tools to improve and professionalize the cultivation of walnut trees, such as tools that can help record the performance of trees and record the inputs such as labor and fertilization.
- Tools that prove the ecosystem benefits of agroforestry. Accurate prediction of ecosystem services of walnut production as part of a dairy farm helps to substantiate the importance of setting up value chains.
- Tools to help parties in the value chain find each other, for example a map on which entrepreneurs can find each other, but also where suppliers are located and what their offer is.

- Matching supply and demand of walnut trees and cultivars for the coming years so that growers can meet the needs of agroforestry farmers.
- Tools that help to introduce agroforestry to the public and actively help to promote agroforestry to consumers and policy makers.

6 Results: United Kingdom

6.1 Description of the UK living lab

The UK living lab is focused on an area covering part of Eastern England and the East Midlands. It is primarily an arable area. The composition of the UK Living lab includes four farmers (one arable farmer/entrepreneur, one arable farmer, one arable farmer/researcher, and one estate farmer), two supply chain actors, and two representatives of government.

The baseline cropping system chosen for the value chain mapping exercise was an arable farm focused on production of wheat, barley, oilseed rape and field beans.

On 10 November 2023, a workshop was organised at Whitehall Farm where Stephen Briggs manages an organic silvoarable system comprising apple with cereals. However the focus of the value chain mapping exercise was the recent establishment of a silvoarable system at Hope Farm which is managed on a commercial basis by the Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB). For the mapping exercise, those present included the two people who manage Hope Farm, a farmer/consultant, a farmer/researcher, a consultant, and a representative from the UK Forestry Commission who is currently developing a new agroforestry support scheme for England.

Figure 6. The workshop in the UK included a range of stakeholders

Because most of the members of the living lab had previously met each other and time limitations, an ice breaking activity was not conducted. The needs and expectations of those in the agroforestry value chain, as well as opportunities to enhance the value chain were discussed with the group.

Figure 8. Value chain map of the baseline arable system at Hope Farm in the UK

Figure 9. Value chain map of Hope Farm in the UK after integration of an agroforestry system

6.3 Challenges and opportunities in the UK

The participants appeared to be fully engaged in the value chain mapping activity and during the process there was a wide range of conversations. The farmers that took part in the workshop listed the following challenges:

- It is difficult to add value to commodities because of the large-scale markets
- It would be useful to know the scope and scale of opportunities with crops such as apples from agroforestry, and nuts.
- There remained some uncertainties about the implications of agriculture/tree cover regulations such as the extent of canopy cover and woodland definitions.
- Identifying markets for wood from farms remains difficult. However one participant highlighted a market tool for hardwood timber in Scotland produced by the Association of Scottish Hardwood Sawmillers (ASHS).

When the opportunities to enhance the value chain of agroforestry products were discussed, the following ideas were identified:

- Changing feed beans for human consumption beans.
- Changing feed wheat for milling wheat and securing certification. Because the farm is managed by RSPB, the RSPB's Fair to Nature certification programme (RSPB 2023) is of particular interest. It may also be possible to engage specialised millers in open market contracts.
- In terms of processing apples, there was an interest in mobile apple processing units.
- There was an interest in farm-level carbon accounting and potential opportunities for carbon trading.
- There was interest in certifying a wider range of farm outputs through the Fair to Nature certification programme.

7 Results: Finland

7.1 Description of the Finnish living lab

The Living labs in Finland comprises four farmers (two arable farmers and two livestock farmers), two teachers from a vocational school and a University of Applied Sciences, one representative from the Finnish Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, one farm advisor, and three researchers.

The principal agricultural products grown on the farms include cereals and sheep for meat. However for the value chain study, the focus was on the value chain for cereals. In order to provide context for the study, the value chain analysis considered the case of an arable farm. This farm is different from an arable farm mentioned in descriptions of the work of the Finish Living Lab who established agroforestry in Autumn 2022. The sheep farmers who were present had been practising agroforestry for several years.

A workshop to progress the value-chain mapping was held on 4 December 2023. No specific ice breaking activities were needed because the participants knew each other. Likewise the speed dating activity was not implemented so that the workshop could focus on the value chain mapping.

7.2 Schematic representation of an agroforestry value chain in Finland

The value chain mapping was conducted in an interview with one farmer who is one of the owners of the farm. The session started with a short introduction explaining the value chain concept and the overall aim of the activity. The researcher carrying out the interview was familiar with the farm and based on knowledge collected earlier in the project, a basic value chain was constructed prior to the interview to guide the discussion. During the interview, the farmer and the interviewer went through the basic value chain, inconsistencies were removed, and missing details were added. To obtain a detailed value chain description, interview questions aimed at identifying the main inputs, products and services of the farm, which actors are involved and to depict the flow of money. During the interview, a lot more detail was added to the original basic value chain and a more detailed value chain map was created (Figure 10).

7.3 Strengths and weaknesses

After the value chain mapping exercise, the farmer was asked to indicate the main difficulties and barriers that occur in daily farm management. Strengths (what works well) and weaknesses (what does not work well) were discussed.

Strengths (what is working well)

- Knowledge: The farmers have good knowledge of the system and spend a significant amount of time searching for knowledge and share this with other farmers.
- Production: The farmers are happy with the production system. They invested a lot of time in improving the sustainability of their system and they are satisfied with how it works. The system works more or less as planned.

Figure 10. Finnish value chain mapping exercise

Four additional strengths were:

- **Agroecology:** The farmers are happy that the production system is focused on agroecology and this has created a more sustainable system. Before changing to agroecological methods, the soil was degraded and contained almost no organic matter. A shift to agroecological methods has clearly improved farm sustainability and the overall condition of the fields. The system is also more resilient, e.g. to drought damage and wind erosion.
- **Economy:** The farm is economically viable. The farm has low production costs and little external inputs.
- **Supply of inputs is fine.** The farmers have good connections with suppliers (e.g. machinery, seeds) and a maintenance network.
- **Good relations with customers.**

Weaknesses (what is not working well)

- **Lack of marketing skills:** The farmers feel they lack the necessary marketing skills for selling their products. In addition, they also lack the time to improve the marketing and their marketing skills.
- **No on-farm processing:** The farm is mainly selling raw materials without any further processing. For example, there is no grain processing. A higher added value could be generated by improving on-farm processing. In addition, the farmers have no time for hiring more personnel to help with and improve on-farm processing.

7.4 Challenges (threats) and opportunities

In a second step, future opportunities for how the farm can improve its business operations were discussed. Here, the farmer identified solutions to address the weaknesses and the threats. The identified solutions will provide an opportunity to upgrade the existing value chain in the near future.

Threats (obstacles to the business)

- **Climate change:** The impacts of climate change have had some effects of farming in Finland although compared to other countries these effects have been relatively minor. Nevertheless, there have been problems with summer drought, spring flooding and overly wet fields during the harvesting season in autumn. In addition, strong winds are more frequent. These adverse impacts of climate change are expected to increase in severity soon.
- **War:** Russia's war in Ukraine had several negative impacts on the Finnish farming sector. Fuel and energy prices have increased a lot, and this has increased production costs. As a consequence, the profitability of farming has been very negatively affected and many farmers had to quit. Most of the artificial fertilizers were imported from Russia and all imports have totally stopped. This led to an increased demand for domestic organic fertilizers which in turn caused scarcity of organic fertilizer. It is highly uncertain how the future situation in Russia will develop but as it is the closest neighbouring country it probably will continue to have an effect on Finland for a very long time.
- **Politics:** It is very uncertain what the current shift in Finnish politics as well as similar trends in other European countries will bring.

Main upgrading opportunities

- **Direct marketing:** Direct marketing of grain or via a cooperative would be an interesting opportunity. There are existing food cooperatives such as Reko. Reko is a network facilitating

direct sales of local, and very often also organic products. Solution: Linking to an existing network or creation of a new network of like-minded farmers.

- Seedling production: There would be an opportunity for seedling production by establishing a tree seedling nursery. Tree seedlings could include species which are currently not very well available, for example walnut and hazel seedlings. Solution/new technology needed: An irrigation system for the tree nursery would be needed. In addition, this would need some reorganization and renovation of some farm buildings.
- Advisory services: The farmers are currently already offering advisory services but there would be a large opportunity to develop these further, for example by offering courses for farmers. Currently there are no advisory services available for starting new agroforestry systems. Farmers are interested in agroforestry but there are no advisors who can help with this. The interviewed farmer would have this knowledge and there would be a great opportunity to develop more advisory services. In Finland, there is a system which entitles every farm in Finland to spend a certain amount on advisory services each year. Solution/new technology needed: Expand the farm and its services via knowledge networks. For this, participation in projects and knowledge networks (e.g. DIGITAF, AFINET, AF4EU, EURAF, other national networks) is very important. It would also require some social activity (events, workshops) and participation in technology discussions.

8 Results: Czechia

8.1 Description of the Czech living lab

The Czech living lab includes eight farmers, three researchers, two advisors, two value chain actors and one policy maker. The focus of the case study farm system is beef, fruit and vegetable production. Some elements of agroforestry are present on the farm, but other activities are being adopted.

A value chain mapping activity was conducted on 17 October 2023 with 8-10 participants, with the resulting map being refined by two researchers. Because most of the participants already knew each other an ice breaking activity was not included. However the speed dating activity to develop a needs and expectation matrix was completed.

8.2 Needs and expectations

When the farmers met with farmers, their needs included the sharing of information and agroforestry experiences, with an expectation of learning from errors and improving the management of trees (Table 3). The discussion between farmers and advisers covered administrative issues and the how agroforestry could be established without subsidy. There was also a focus on the valuation of ecosystem services, agricultural processing, and erosion control measures.

The discussions between farmers and researchers focused on ways of working together, including sharing of data and tree species selection. When the farmer and the value chain actor discussed their needs and expectations, there was an interest in helping with planning and the prediction of droughts. The discussions between farmers and policy makers focused on understanding the needs for farmer and the opportunities for simplification of administration requirements and flexibility in agroforestry design.

Table 3. Needs and expectations of the farmers between themselves and with different groups

	Needs	Expectations
Farmer with farmer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share agroforestry experiences Exchange of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Networking Management of trees Learning from errors
Farmer with advisers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing agroforestry without any subsidy Knowledge sharing Ecosystem services valuation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agricultural processing Erosion control measures Administration of the agroforestry establishment
Farmer with researcher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sharing data with researchers Administration of subsidies Joint projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connection with the research sector Tree species selection Involvement in research projects
Farmer with value chain actor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand what farmers need Which data can help farmers Help with planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prediction of droughts
Farmer with policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simplification of policy and administration Understand the needs of farmers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperation with officials Flexibility in agroforestry design

8.3 Schematic representation of an agroforestry value chain in Czechia

An initial value chain focused on the inputs and the outputs of the Czechian case study farm was created (Figure 11). Compared with some of the other value chains, there was also a focus on societal and landscape benefits from the farm and an emphasis on the enthusiasm of the farmer (Figure 12).

Figure 11. Schematic diagram of the value chain of a selected Czechian farm

8.4 Challenges and opportunities

Most of the farmers in the Czech Living Lab have some experience with agroforestry, they either have some agroforestry elements on their farm or want to establish agroforestry soon. They have very good knowledge about the ecosystem services of agroforestry, and what agroforestry could bring to the landscape and society, however they lack any means to place a value on those externalities. They do not place much value on tree productivity except for fruit trees. However, they see a lot of challenges in agroforestry implementation, such as more complex administration and heavier bureaucratic burden, lack of knowledge and skill for tree growing on agricultural land, high investment costs, etc.

In the workshop, they express their needs in the form of networking with other farmers and researchers including knowledge exchange and advisory service creation. With a new support measure for agroforestry currently running in Czechia, they often mention the low flexibility of this measure and expect help with administration. They also expect help with suitable tree selection for their farm particular characteristics and conditions, and a design tool for the establishment of agroforestry. The primary value-chain vision is quite straightforward, seeing the potential contribution of agroforestry not only in tangible products (e.g. fruit, vegetable, eggs, and timber), but also in societal benefits (recreation, employment, education) and landscape conservation (ecosystem services).

Figure 12. Digital version of the value chain mapping exercise of the Czech Living Lab

9 Results: Germany

9.1 Description of the German living lab

The German living lab is based in the state of Brandenburg. The Living lab comprises five farmers and producers, seven business and service providers, three end customers and buyers, two members of the general public, six representatives from NGOs and research organisations, and three people involved in policy development or administration (Figure 13).

Figure 13. The composition of the German Living Lab

The agricultural value chain was based on the wide variety of agroforestry innovations that have been implemented on Domin Farm which is described in DigitAF Deliverable (Figure 14). The agricultural operations include arable cropping, grassland management, and animal husbandry (various poultry, pig fattening, cattle breeding and fattening systems).

Figure 14. Map of agroforestry areas on Domin Farm. Area of arable land are surrounded by a yellow border. Areas of permanent grassland are surrounded by a blue border: **A**: short rotation poplar, **B**: riparian buffer strip; **C**: short rotation crop; **D**: mixed hardwood species; **E**: Silvopastoral system including chicken and black locust; **F**: Orchard; **G**: orchard meadow.

The workshop involved 26 participants, with the resulting map being refined by one farmer and two researchers. An initial value chain map was first constructed in September 2023 and validated with the farmer during a farm visit in October 2023 and a subsequent online meeting. In a third step, external or non-direct participants of the value chain were added to the map in December 2023.

The attendees to the workshop were invited due to their distinct expertise. The workshop participants further explored broadening potentials in the field of agroforestry during the workshop, for example biochar production and various wood utilisation pathways, such as Short Rotation Coppice (SRC) for energy production, oriented strand board (OSB) production or even more complex applications such as the use of lignocellulose in the production of biogas in a co-fermenting process with manure. An ice-breaking session was therefore conducted in the sense of short introductory presentations highlighting various pathways in the value chain.

Similar, as the participants were invited due to their expertise, a short introductory round was done additionally to the short introductory presentations, thus further strengthening the network and exchanging valuable contact information.

Figure 15. Impression from the German Living Lab listening to an online guest (Photo: J. Günzel).

Figure 16. Group work presentation (Photo: R. Hübner).

9.2 Schematic representation of an agroforestry value chain in Germany

The researcher carrying out the interview was very familiar with the farm and based on knowledge collected earlier in the project, a basic value chain was facilitated in a workshop lead by PP Cranfield University and constructed prior to the interview to facilitate the process. In an exploratory way, starting from the various types of agroforestry systems in place since 2015. The preliminary results of the value chain mapping were – running through a streamlining procedure with the PPs from other Living Labs – verified with the farmer and experts from DeFAF. As a result, a mind map was developed (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Graphical overview on the value chain at the German Living Lab

Three main components of activities in the value chain were identified: 1) alley cropping-system, 2) fruit tree-system, and 3) animal husbandry-system. Besides these three main systems, the Living Lab-farm analysed is active in a number of research and education activities actively engaging with various stakeholder groups.

- *Alley cropping-system*: comprised of various fast-growing tree species mainly grown as energy wood, such as common osier / basket willow, hybrid-poplar (Max III, Bakan, FW II, Vesten), and black locust. The staple crops grown in between are silage maize, green rye, winter rye, and as an experimental crop, teff.
- *Animal husbandry-system*: located on permanent grassland grazed by a heard of mother cows including their offspring and used as a chicken run. The tree species on grassland are willow, poplar, and alder. In addition, a section of the black locust planting serves as a retreat area for chicken, geese and ducks.
- *Fruit tree-system*: fruit production (apple, pear, elderberry, serviceberry) and the production of valuable timber (Turkish hazel, grey poplar, field maple, and chestnut, partly in rows and partly on small batches/groups, completes the farm.

9.3 Strengths and weaknesses

In terms of an analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of the system, it was decided to focus on an alley cropping system, covering: 1) general aspects of agroforestry, 2) Biochar production and application (Figure 18), and 3) wood chip production for energy/material use (Figure 19).

Figure 18. Biochar production and application: four pyrolysis reactors at the farm (Photo: T. Domin).

Figure 19. Wood chips that can be used for energy/material substitution purposes. (Photo: T. Domin).

Strengths (what is working well)

General aspects of agroforestry: in addition to the important yield benefits (improved water balance, reduction of erosion, and promotion of beneficial organisms), benefits for the promotion of biodiversity, soil structure and adaptation to climate change play a major role here. Five states in Germany have plans to establish an initial investment cost funding scheme in Pillar II, including in Brandenburg, where the Living Lab is situated. Funding in Brandenburg is within reach and promising to be interesting for farmers, in detail these are:

- Up to 1.290 €/ha wooded area in case of fast-growing wood in short rotation (§6 Art 3 GAPDZV);
- Up to 3.869 €/ha wooded area in the case of planting of shrubs;
- Up to 4.430 €/ha in the case of planting of trees for food or stem wood production used for both purposes;
- Up to 5.000 €/ha in case of planting of trees for food or stem wood production used for both purposes with additional shrubs in the undergrowth;
- In addition, a top-up of 270 €/ha in the case of the planting of more than five species of wooded plants per ha in the system.

Biochar: there are two pyrolysis plants on the farm for the batch production of charcoal and biochar (originally four batches). Trials applying charcoal/biochar are being carried out on the arable land plots in the alley cropping system to test the possible effects of biochar in agroforestry systems. The trials are designed to investigate different application rates and to differentiate between areas on which inoculated charcoal was applied and charcoal without inoculation in terms of yields, particularly concerning water storage capacity. It is worth noting that the yields could be increased, especially with the activated biochar, but a precise evaluation of the results is still pending. On the positive side: long-term soil improvement (depending on how the biochar is used, increase/stabilised yields (compare costs/benefits), reduction of emissions, improvement of economic efficiency on the farm (especially with CO₂ certificates).

Wood chip production for energy/material use: There is great potential here for a more independent municipal and CO₂-neutral heat supply with wood from the field. A village/municipality, a local energy company or a co-operative that works together with agriculture are potential partners. The mayor from Thallwitz (Wurzener Land) explained how multi-utilisation concepts the basis for long-term cooperation between village and farmer could be.

Weaknesses (what is not working well)

General aspects of agroforestry: the current Strategic Plan of the German federal government as part of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) assumes that the area of agroforestry woodland on German fields will be around 200,000 hectares by 2026. At the end of 2023, there were only around 56 ha nationwide. This is presumably the result of rules and obligations of Pillar I-measure, specifically EcoScheme #3, that are perceived as too strict and the remuneration of 200€/ha wooded area as not convincing enough for farmers to do agroforestry, especially as the establishment funding is not (yet) in place. Although in Reg. (EU) No. 1143/2014 and (EU) 2019/1262 from 25.07.2019 it is stated that all other trees species can be grown and used in agroforestry systems, the negative list in Germany poses a burden on farmers. Specially in the state of Brandenburg, where the black locust would be the ideal tree for agroforestry in times of climate crisis.

Biochar: suitable solutions are still lacking in some cases: the cascade utilisation with several pyrolysis ovens that was envisaged turned out not to be applicable, meaning that only two ovens are currently being used. There is a lack of experience on the part of the users, in some cases. In addition, the manufacturing company only supplied limited components and the installation

was reduced. The entire process ran unsatisfactorily with the comparatively fine-structured wood chippings, as the system became partially blocked. Orderly process control was not possible and filling and emptying the small batch systems was very time-consuming. In summary, weaknesses of the system: only supplies biochar, no use of the excess heat, the use of different biomass possible, but not advisable, fluctuating quality, cumbersome handling, throughput too low.

Wood chip production for energy/material use: with a view to the wood value chain from agroforestry with fast-growing tree species, municipalities should seek more dialogue with their farmers.

9.4 Challenges (threats) and opportunities

An opportunity with agroforestry is to communicate it as land utilisation systems with numerous advantages and a relatively long lifespan – even beyond the use of the wood for energy or material purposes (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Alley cropping system with poplar, black locust and various hardwood species, interspersed with cropland (Photo: R. Hübner).

Three challenges to agroforestry were also examined in terms of general aspects, biochar production, and wood chip production.

General aspects of agroforestry: there is a very high risk, that due to the financial stop of payment no new agroforestry will be set in place after 1 January 2024. In the future, it is important to clarify that the establishment and utilisation of agroforestry systems is continue being supported in the CAP. Another threat comes from the potential legal interaction with other rules and regulations, especially from the nature protection laws in Germany. There is a certain legal uncertainty, on how environmental regulations could threaten agroforestry systems now and in the future.

Biochar production: in terms of practical application and the associated challenges, biochar production currently remains trapped in an experimental stage, especially as long as the technical difficulties cannot be resolved. In summary, heat supply with pyrolysis is possible (has a low efficiency), pyrolysis must be suitable for operation (batch process/automated plant).

Wood chip production for energy/material use: municipalities and energy suppliers who buy wood from farmers and feed it into their local or district heating networks in the form of wood chips are sometimes struggling with the legal and administrative burden. The instalment can only succeed with a political and financial backup from policy and administration. From the perspective of agriculture, farmers want security in the form of long-term lease agreements with wood purchase guarantees of up to 15 years – often this is not possible to guarantee by

the business partners. Vattenfall Energy Crops GmbH is an example of a company offering long-term co-operation agreements with agricultural businesses for the supply of heat to Berlin. The farmer leases the land and prepares the soil, while Energy Crops assumes the costs and risk for planting, maintenance, harvesting and removal.

10 Results: Spain

10.1 Description of the Spanish case study

Although there is not a DigitAF Living lab in space, in the original DigitAF application it was indicated that it would be useful to consider a specific agroforestry value chain system focused on Spain that uses blockchain.

Blockchain technology offers an opportunity to track the value chain of agroecosystems. However, it has been found, that in the dehesa, it is useful when data collection is mostly automatic and there is a strong association among farmers and with other actors. Despite the low level of the digitalisation of the dehesa farms, important progress has been done by dehesa producers, boosted by the operational group SOSTVAN and two collaborative initiatives, IBERCHAIN for the Iberian pig fattened with dehesa acorns, and DEFHESA for the free-range cattle sector. Further detailed description and discussion can be read in the Annex 1.

10.2 Schematic representation of an agroforestry value chain in Spain

The value chain mapping workshop was conducted in a workshop on 25 November 2023 with five farmers that produce several products, but mainly cattle and sheep meat products. The session was facilitated by introducing the topic, explaining the overall aim of the activity, and asking questions where the discussion got stuck. The questions aimed at identifying the main products and services of the farms, which actors are involved and to depict the flow of money. Additionally, two in-person interviews were conducted with farmers that raise Iberian pig and that extract cork from cork oaks. These additional interviews were conducted to fulfil the main gaps detected in the original value chain map and create a complete picture (Figure 21).

The value chain discussion was rich. The participants talked about their main products, the flow of services and money and the barriers and opportunities that they encounter. They pointed the main actors involved and touched upon their general knowledge about the system. They described some stories of successful endeavours regarding the commercialization of products and discussed that there are several opportunities that can help to improve the sustainability of the system.

The value chain discussion was centred on meat products, the main products of the system. The main actors involved were related to animal merchants. They pointed that there is a lack of transparency in the systems, as deals are usually closed at the farm level. So neighbouring farms may receive different prices from the same product. There is an overall lack of association among them, this together with the limitation on prices and the rising cost of inputs, puts the farmers in a dare situation.

Other products of the dehesa were also mentioned, such as game, firewood, honey, or wool. Regarding game, the farmers consider that there is a trade-off between both type of activities. Farms that are dedicated to livestock rearing cannot support high populations of game. On the other side, farms that are mainly use for hunting maintain a low level of livestock as an entry point to receive subsidies. In the case of firewood, honey and wool, the farmers rather than received money for these products, usually bartered them for services or a share of the product. In the case of the wool, this practice is disappearing as the cost of paying the shredders is too high.

Figure 21. Value chain map of the Dehesa farm depicting the flow of products, services, and money

10.3 Strengths and weaknesses

During the mapping process of the value chain, the participants indicated the main difficulties and barriers that they encounter in their day-to-day activities, identifying the opportunities that can arise to overcome these barriers and to exploit other niches in the systems.

The topics covered in the discussion included:

Lack of specific commercialization channels: dehesas provide several ecosystems services and biodiversity conservation, and their products are usually of high quality, but this added value is not included in the price of the products because they are sold in conjunction with other general products which production systems do not account for environmental conservation.

Products of low unitary value: the products do not benefit from the positive externalities of the system. They usually have a low unitary value as the prices does not reflect the environmental benefits of the system.

Lack of a Union: producers act mostly individuals; they face their barriers and challenges at the farm level and do not tackle them as a group. This situation reduces the power of the sector to negotiate with other stakeholders.

Task overload: farmers must do multiple tasks to run their business. This overload does not allow enough time to think about other opportunities and ways to improve the production system.

Lack of local or regional abattoirs: the number of abattoirs has been reduced in recent years. There are extensive areas without any abattoirs which limits the possibilities of commercialization of proximity products.

Society perception of meat products: the increasing awareness of meat products and consumption by society worries the farmers. Society does not perceive the added value of the products of the dehesa.

10.4 Opportunities and threats

New business opportunities were mentioned, such as touristic and educational services, such as doing open days to schools, or payments for carbon credits. Carbon credits are an incipient activity, some farmers are already receiving them, but there is high uncertainty in the system.

Regarding the barriers, the discussion was centred on the distribution and selling of the products. Most indicated that due to the lack of abattoirs, they are forced to distribute their products in other general channels, losing added value. More details are included in section 7.1.3.

The farms require several services for their day-to-day operations. Veterinary services, administration, labour, or machinery were among the most commented ones. As to the machinery, most farmers have their own machinery, sometimes in excess, but also for interventions, they need to rent special equipment.

Services provided by the farms include nature conservation and carbon sequestration. There is an increasing interest in selling carbon credits. Land stewardship is promoted by a local NGO. Those farms that join this program, received in exchange some services, such as the maintenance of ponds. Similarly, regional government compensate the farms that are included in protected areas, such as Natura 2000 network. Most dehesas benefit from this because they are included in the list of Habitats of Interest. Finally, the eco-scheme related to extensive grazing was also mentioned as a source of income.

The following opportunities were discussed:

- Increase the association of the producers to avoid individual discussions with merchants, and ensure a fair price for the same products.
- The production of specific products, to avoid producing general products that has not carried added value.
- Look for opportunities to associate with local retailers and butchers. They explained several examples of success.
- Innovation on products

11 Discussion and conclusions

The results from the case studies are discussed in terms of the facilitation of workshops and the benefits of bringing people together. There is also a discussion of the mapping of value chains. The final section focuses on whether the agroforestry innovations on focusing on new methods or new products. A final section focuses on the different characteristics of long and short value chains.

11.1 Facilitation of the workshops

The focused mapping of value chains was a new activity for most of the stakeholders. In some locations, using “ice-breaking” activities such as those described in Appendix A provided a relaxed “warm” environment where stakeholders from different parts of the value chain were able to share insights and experiences. The protocol therefore provides a useful resource for researchers who are facilitating such activities.

11.2 Benefits of bringing people together

The creation of a living lab environment creates opportunities for unplanned serendipitous outputs. For example, at the UK site the mapping workshop provided an opportunity for a government representative who is involved with creating new agroforestry policies to visit an actual field site and to learn of the constraints faced by farmers. The workshops held across Italy, the Netherlands, Finland, Czechia, and Germany also proved instrumental in bringing farmers together to discuss their agroforestry experiences. These discussions shed light on the multifaceted challenges and opportunities present in the agroforestry value chains.

11.3 Mapping of value chains

Perhaps surprisingly there appear to be relatively few peer-reviewed papers related to the mapping of value chains of food in Europe. This may partly be due to the commercial sensitivity of such information. Hence the activities completed in this report are relatively novel. Moreover, the need to understand food value chains is increasing in importance as food safety and social, environmental, and welfare concerns are being demanded by government, some consumers, and some retailers.

One drive for the mapping of value chains relates to the targets being set by major retailers to ensure that their Scope 3 greenhouse gas emissions are net zero in 2050. For example, in the UK, targets have been set by several of the major food retailers (Sainsbury’s, 2023; Tesco’s, 2021; Waitrose, 2023). Such targets mean that retailers need to understand the source of their products and the impacts of greenhouse gas emissions along each value chain. However, because the focus can be solely on greenhouse gas emissions, other exchanges that take place in the value chain can be missed.

The need for understanding and mapping value chains is also a key feature of the European Commission’s recent regulation 2023/1115 on deforestation-free products (European Commission 2023). Under this regulation, any trader who imports a range of selected products into the EU market, or who is exporting from the EU must be able to prove that their products do not originate from recently deforested land. Although the list is currently restricted to cattle, wood, cocoa, soy, palm oil, coffee, and rubber; it can be anticipated that the need for food processors to understand the geographic source of products is likely to increase.

Although it was not a focus of this particular study, within the farming sector there is also an interest in the proportion of the value added in the food sector by different components of the food value chain. For example, in the USA, the proportion of the “food at home dollar” that is retained by farm producers ranged between 10.4 and 15.4% (USDA, 2023). Individual stakeholders within the food value chain are obviously interested in maximising the proportion of the final value of food (Figure 22). One potential way for individual farmers to maximise the proportion of the final value of home consumed food is to shorten the value chain from producer to consumer.

Figure 22. Annual estimates from 1993 to 2022 of the proportion of the “food at home dollar” in the United States of America that is secured by individual stakeholder groups from domestically produced food. Agribusiness includes upstream suppliers of seed, fertilizers, and farm machinery and farm services (USDA, 2023).

11.4 New methods or new products and services

The focus of the DigitAF project is on the development and use of tools to enhance the practice of agroforestry. In some places, agroforestry is an existing practice but in some locations the integration of trees on farms is new. The level of innovation required to implement new forms of agroforestry can vary between sites. Morel et al. (2020) describes three types of innovation.

1. There are innovations which involving “changing within” existing value chains. For example the Spanish case study focuses on improving traceability of cattle within an existing agroforestry system.
2. Some innovations involve “building outside” existing value chains. For example in the UK, the planting of apple and nut trees on an arable farm means that the farmer needs to find new ways of deriving financial value from the produced apples and nuts. In the UK case, it was anticipated that these markets would be local.

3. Some innovations can involve “playing horizontal” where a farmer will work with another stakeholder such as another farmer in a mutually-beneficial arrangement. For example an arable and livestock farmer may work together so that the arable farmer may gain from the manure produced by animals, and the livestock farmer benefits from the provision of animal feed at reduced cost. Such innovations may operate by changing the linkages within value chains without “directly challenging the vertical organisation of dominant value chains” (Morel et al., 2020).

11.5 Common challenges and diverse opportunities

Across the case studies, several common challenges emerged. Knowledge gaps, bureaucratic obstacles, and conflicts with environmentalists were recurrent themes. Farmers expressed concerns about measurement applicability and difficulties in applying existing metrics. The distinction between agricultural areas and forests, coupled with issues surrounding fence authorization and forest grazing, added to these complexities.

On the other hand, discussions also highlighted numerous opportunities. Digital tools, such as block chain-related technologies, were recognized as potentially useful for data collection, even though their current use was limited. The potential benefits of strong local or regional consortiums, similar to Parmigiano Reggiano in Italy, were acknowledged. Direct marketing, seedling production, and expanded advisory services emerged as potential routes for growth and progress.

11.6 Short or long value chains and accreditation

Across the case studies, there were also differences in the length of value chains and these can have an impact on the relevance of certification. These be illustrated by two extreme types:

Local markets: in the case, the quantities of produce can be relatively small and there can be opportunities for using small-scale processing facilities, and promoting alternative food systems. Such a process is regularly used by organic producers (Morel et al., 2020). In such cases, the consumer can benefit from the knowledge that a food product is locally produced from a recognised supplier, and the farmer can receive a higher price than if the products was sold on a wholesale market. Hence, it is noteworthy that in the UK case study, the intention was primarily to market the new agroforestry products of apples and nuts at a local scale.

Commodity markets: for many commodity markets the value chains can be long and can even include the export of crops. Such systems typically involve large agribusinesses and there typically is no premium for local production. Within a commodity market, there are still often minimal standards for the way in which food is produced, but these can often be minimal. For selected products, environmental or welfare-based accreditation schemes can be important in order to secure specific contracts. The blockchain system described for Spain is an example of an attempt to receive a price premium for beef products. In the UK case-study, there was interest in how wheat could be grown as milling wheat to gain a premium within the RSPB’s Fair to Nature certification programme (RSPB 2023).

11.7 Innovation strategies, socio-economic and environmental considerations

Innovation strategies varied across countries. Some focused on refining existing value chains by improving traceability, while others explored entirely new value chains, like planting apple and nut trees in arable farms. Collaborations between arable and livestock farmers showcased the possibilities of "playing horizontal". The case study in Finland, characterized by strengths in knowledge, production, and agroecology, identified marketing and on-farm processing as weak points. In that context, the emphasis was placed on adapting and optimizing linkages within value chains to maximize benefits. The German case study, which had three main components of agroforestry of alley cropping, fruit tree systems, and animal husbandry, highlighted the need for diverse approaches tailored to local contexts.

In Spain, concerns about societal perceptions of meat products and the lack of specific commercialization channels were discussed. Despite dehesas providing valuable ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation, products were undervalued due to being sold alongside general products. In various countries, there was a growing interest in carbon credits as a potential revenue source. Moreover, some farms engaged in nature conservation efforts, participating in programmes that compensated them for services like pond maintenance and land stewardship.

Discussions in Finland emphasized the need for future changes in the Common Agricultural Policy to consider the challenges of biodiversity management on farms. The necessity for agroforestry funding schemes to allow for maintenance, not just establishment, was also highlighted. The study in Germany echoed these sentiments stressing the importance of continued support for agroforestry. The German study also emphasised the challenge of lists of tree species which were not allowed to be planted in agroforestry systems. The legal uncertainty around environmental regulations emerged as a shared concern across nations.

Conclusions

The agroforestry value chains in Europe are dynamic and context-specific, shaped by a myriad of challenges and opportunities. The collaborative efforts of farmers, facilitated by participatory research such as these mapping workshops, provide a foundation for addressing these challenges and optimizing value chains. Innovations within existing systems, such as improved traceability, and explorations of new value chains, exemplify the adaptive nature of agroforestry practices. To sustain these efforts, policy support through the CAP and clear regulations that encourage agroforestry development are critical. The process of all European economies towards decarbonization and increased sustainability can be helped if the substantial benefits of agroforestry are recognised and valued by suppliers, purchasers, and consumers through the value chain.

12 References

- European Commission (2023) Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 on deforestation-free products. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/forests/deforestation/regulation-deforestation-free-products_en
- Kaplinsky, R., Morris, M. (2000) A Handbook for Value Chain Research. Brighton, UK: Institute of Development Studies. 106 pp
http://asiandrivers.open.ac.uk/documents/Value_chain_Handbook_RKMM_Nov_2001.pdf
- Morel, K., Revoyron, E., Cristobal, M.S., Baret, P.V. (2020) Innovating within or outside dominant food systems? Different challenges for contrasting crop diversification strategies in Europe. PLoS One 15:1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229910>
- RSPB (Royal Society for the Protection of Birds) (2023) Fair to Nature. <https://fairtonature.org/>
- Sainsbury's (2023) Reduce carbon emissions. <https://www.about.sainsburys.co.uk/sustainability/better-for-the-planet/carbon>
- Stein, C., Barron, J. (2017) Mapping actors along value chains: integrating visual network research and participatory statistics into value chain analysis. Research for Development Learning Series 5. CGIAR Research Program on Water, Land and Ecosystems (WLE). 28 pp. doi: 10.5337/2017.216
https://www.iwmi.cgiar.org/Publications/wle/r4d/wle_research_for_development-learning_series-5.pdf
- Tescos (2021) Tesco commits to net zero emissions from its supply chain and products by 2050. <https://www.tescopl.com/tesco-commits-to-net-zero-supply-chain-and-products-by-2050/>
- USDA (2023) Food dollar series. <https://www.ers.usda.gov/data-products/food-dollar-series/>
- Voinov, A., Jenni, K., Gray, S., Kolagani, N., Glynn, P.D., Bommel, P., Prell, C., Zellner, M., Paolisso, M., Jordan, R., Sterling, E., Schmitt Olabisi, L., Giabbanelli, P.J., Sun, Z., Le Page, C., Elsworth, S., BenDor, T.K., Hubacek, K., Laursens, B.K., Jetter, A., Basco-Carrera, L., Singer, A., Young, L., Jessica Brunacinic, Smajgl, A., (2018) Tools and methods in participatory modeling: Selecting the right tool for the job. Environmental Modelling and Software 109, 232–255.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2018.08.028>
- Waitrose (2023) Climate action. <https://www.johnlewispartnership.co.uk/csr/our-strategy/climate-action.html>

APPENDIX A: Protocol for the Value Chain Mapping

The text below describes a protocol that was established for the value chain mapping.

Value chain mapping

The methodology to be utilized by all Living Labs is focused and aimed at mapping agroforestry value chains in a participatory manner. The following sections describe the methodology proposal to be adopted by all Living Labs leaders to produce comparable and interesting results. Given the diversity and the heterogeneity of the living labs and the connected value chains, the proposed methodology can be slightly changed and adapted to the specific situation and living labs. The material and the form proposed in the appendix would like to give you an idea of the information output that can be collected at the end of the workshop.

The role of the facilitator: an overview

Your role as a facilitator will be to **facilitate the process of knowledge and idea sharing** among all Living Lab members participating in the activities. In short, you will have to:

- i) Prevent that the conversation(s) go **off-topic** but rather stay focused on the objective(s)
- ii) Prevent the Living Lab members from not interacting due to **shyness and/or boredom**.
- iii) **Record information/feedback/ideas** to be included in the **report** for better data interpretation/ to accompany the schematic outputs which will be a speed dating matrix (suggested not mandatory) and a value chain map.

McBrown (2021) identifies seven points you can follow to achieve an effective facilitation process. These are:

1. Set the boundaries:

Firstly, it is extremely important to clarify the workshop rules and objectives. The **aims** need to be reasonable with the time allocated to the participatory activity. Moreover, the activity should start with a clarification of the **outcome**, before starting the LL, ask yourself “which will be the outcomes of this workshop”?

In our case, the main output will be the mapping of the value chain of the selected Living Lab value chain/s. During the mapping activity, stakeholders should give their opinion regarding the problems and obstacles that limits the adoption of agroforestry practices and options for the transition to agroforestry.

2. Remain impartial

The objectives of the workshop need to be clear, but the outcome is the co-design process. Generally, researchers have already an outcome in their mind, this should influence the participatory process but not dominate it. The facilitator needs to encourage all stakeholders to talk. The group should feel as they have been able to reach a consensus by themselves, with limited support from the facilitator.

3. Understand group dynamics:

It is important to observe the group dynamics using your intuition and your instincts to create a productive and relaxing atmosphere. The facilitator should be able to understand and capture the process. Questions made by the facilitator should help to challenge, clarify, and concentrate on certain points.

4. Use your personal style:

The style, the energy and the personality of the facilitator has a strong influence on the Living Lab outputs and results. A facilitator should have an empathic personal presence to be respected and trusted by the group. Of extreme importance is the ability of a facilitator in dealing with incidents that might happen.

5. Intervene when appropriate:

The facilitator should always pay attention to what is happening, being able to solve conflicts. Sometimes is better to be quiet before intervening. An intervention does not necessarily require talking: a look, a smile or a nod can be enough to support or change what it is happening. Be careful in challenging the group by asking difficult questions, the situation might become tricky to handle.

6. Handling difficult situations:

One of the trickiest tasks of the facilitator is dealing with difficult people and conflicts. In case of conflict, it is not the reason of the disagreement what matters but how people react to it. To solve the situations there are tactics and skills you can develop. In case of difficult situations, it is advisable to have a coffee break, change the scenery, working in pairs or brainstorm the issue involved. In case of only one disruptive individual, you can choose to confront directly that person.

7. Practise, practise, practise!

Facilitation skills can be developed with practice. Some people might be more prone to have the facilitation skills, however, observation, listening, reading body language, understanding human behaviour and take a step back to the content can all be achieved through practice.

Ice breaking activities (suggested)

In this section, we present a few optional ice-breaking activities. The main goal is to help the participants feel more comfortable and relaxed enough to provide input. This activity helps stakeholders, especially farmers, to be involved in the discussion encouraging them to participate actively. Some examples are (but feel free to use others, and specify it into the report):

Penny stories

This icebreaker is made with the aim of encourage conversation allowing peers to relate to one another. For this icebreaker game you need penny/cents with different years printed on it. This icebreaker starts with each team member taking a penny and introducing themselves with their name and job title. Then, using the year printed on the penny they choose, each team member then shares a story about an event they attended during that year.

"Find someone who"

"Find someone who" is a game where each team member writes on a piece of paper a personal peculiarity or an activity they do. The pieces of paper are then mixed and redistributed to all the team members. Each team member must speak to the others to find the name of the person related to that activity/peculiarity written on the piece of paper. The "find someone who" game is similar to the introduction interview icebreaker, and it can be used for any sized group. Once a team member has found the designated person, they can introduce themselves to the rest of the group. This icebreaker requires the use of strategy skills and problem-solving.

"Find two people"

In the "Find two people" icebreaking activity, it is necessary to create a list of descriptors. After that, each person involved needs to talk with each member to find those who share characteristics. For example, an item on the list may be someone with the same shoe size or someone who has been to a certain number of states. "Find two people" is an active icebreaker that allows team members to encourage relationships.

"Two truths and a lie"

A helpful icebreaker for introductions and learning more about coworkers is the "two truths and a lie" game. In turn each person shares two truthful details about themselves and one lie. The rest of the group must guess which statement about them is a lie.

Participatory value chain mapping: core activity

Objective of the activities

The objective of the core activity is to identify and map the actors and major flows of money, products and services in AF value chains with a co-design approach. The main output(s) of the activity should be schematic "map(s)" of the flow of goods and services in the value chain associated for the established Living Labs and an adequate supporting material containing:

- Schematic description of the participants (Living Lab description)
- Supporting material explaining any changes/ adaptation to the agreed-upon methodology

First core activity: Agroforestry "SPEED DATING" session

The purpose of the "speed dating" session is to encourage participants of the Living Lab to know each other further, by speaking to each other for 3 to 5 minutes. Figure A.1 shows an example of speed dating methodology for:

- 20 participants (10 fixed+ 10 rotating)
- 3-5 minutes for each speed dating session
- 5 minutes for 10 times: 50 minutes total (1h)

Figure A.1. Speed dating diagram (Stanford Graduate School of Education 2022)

Then participants will be divided into couples. Each couple has five minutes available to get to know the mate completing the form of needs and expectations regarding agroforestry systems. The idea is to let different stakeholders, representing different categories, (i.e. farmer vs. advisor; farmer vs. researcher; advisor vs. researcher) tell each other their respective needs and expectations. To give an example: a farmer might ask to do research to have more evidence about the effectiveness of agroforestry while the researcher might need real data regarding the economics of a farm.

The first activity consists in having all participants fill in the Needs and Expectations form (Figure A.2, printing version available in Annex, section A2) and therefore record both their expectations and needs with regards to the other participant, and vice versa. "Needs" are linked to current (short-

term) issues or necessities with the other stakeholders, while “expectations” identify something related to the future.

Name and role: (me)				
Name and role	(their) Needs	(their) Expectations	(my) Needs	(my) Expectations
person 1				
person 2				
person 3				
person 4				
person 5				

Figure A.2. Needs and Expectations form to be given and filled in by each participant

Second core activity: Value chain mapping exercise: methodology

Each Living Lab is comprised of a unique set of stakeholders and represents potentially very different value chain types. In order to generate comparable results, it is good to proceed with a harmonious and flexible methodology.

To produce a schematic overview of the value chain in the Living Labs, a participatory modeling approach was selected. Specifically, we selected a concept mapping methodology, which is a qualitative modelling type that allows conceptualization (Voinov et al., 2018). Concept maps are graphical representations of organized knowledge that visually illustrate the relationships among elements within a knowledge domain.

What is a value chain? What are we trying to map?

According to the literature, a value chain describes “the full range of activities which are required to bring a product or service from conception, through the different phases of production (involving a combination of physical transformation and input of various producer services), delivery to final consumers, and final disposal after use” (Kaplinsky and Morris, 2000).

Figure A.3. Graphical abstract of a value chain (Kaplinsky and Morris 2000)

Real life scenarios are of course much more complex, involving numerous steps and intermediaries. Additionally, a particular value chain may feed into several different value chains. The goal of this activity is not to produce an accurate estimation of costs and monetary flows or life cycle costing analysis, but rather to capture stakeholder perceptions regarding the main goods and services in the value chain of Each Living Lab.

For this reason, simplifications and assumptions will have to be done, with the main ones being reported in the supplementary material, giving priority to the products or services regarded with most importance by the stakeholders involved in the co-design activity. Impressions and information collected by the facilitators during the activities will also help the researchers to better understand stakeholders' perceptions in barriers that limits the adoption of agroforestry and its potential benefits.

Two aspects that it is useful to define are:

- System boundaries (represented graphically)
- Our "functional unit/s": the product/s and/or service/s the value chain refers to, i.e. beef, timber, cereal crops, carbon storage, ecosystem services, etc.

Value chain mapping exercise: operational steps

Materials

The mapping exercise should be conducted using low-cost materials including:

- Sheets of paper in a big size suitable for drawing the value chain map.
- Sticky notes of various colors to jot down activities and actors involved.
- Pens of various colors to sketch the connections among different actors in the chain.
- Illustrations, photographs, diagrams, or symbols to represent distinct analytical dimensions on the map (optional).
- Tools for recording data, such as notebooks and cameras for taking photographs.

Structure of working group and facilitation questions

The participants should work in a team in one group (therefore producing only one map). Facilitators will have to keep track of the order of people willing to speak. They can bring ideas regarding all parts of the value chain, regardless of their professional role.

The mapping process consists of the following main steps:

1. Drawing the value chain map, recording: value chain activities, actors, links, and context.
2. Analysis, interpretation, and discussion of the map together with research participants.

The following are examples of questions the facilitators should pose to the group(s) to encourage the value-chain mapping activity. Additional questions can of course be posed to have a more tailored approach to each Living Lab (please include additional questions and methodologies in the report).

- Who are the actors involved?
- What activities are they involved in?
- What are the main flows of money across the value chain?
- What are the main flows of products and services across the value chain?
- What are the inputs and outputs of each activity?
- What are the constraints and challenges associated with each activity?
- What are the opportunities for improving the efficiency, profitability, and sustainability of the value chain?

Reminder: a good rule of thumb is, as a facilitator, to note down and register as much information as possible in a schematic way and then annotate it in the resulting report. Here is a generic mapping canvas that can help to guide the mapping process, as reported in the resources made available by the CGIAR Research Program on Water, Land and Ecosystems (Stein and Barron 2017).

Figure A.4. Mapping canvas

A possible strategy for creating a value chain map

We propose the following strategy based on Stein and Barron (2017):

1. Make sure to ask the participants to sign a declaration to comply with GDPR rules.
2. Fill in the needs and expectations form with the participants. “Needs” are linked to current (short-term) issues or necessities, while “expectations” identify something related to the future.
3. Define the activities necessary to bring a product from inception to consumption and write them on sticky notes and then place them on the map (e.g. for beef in an agroforestry system, the activities could be: cattle rearing, slaughtering, feed production transportation, and certifications). The value chain activities can be placed either according to chronological order or depending on where they occur spatially (e.g. for a very short, locally-based value chain). Figure A.5 shows an example of post-it and colors that can be used during this activity.

Figure A.5. Example of colour code and materials used for the mapping (yellow sticky note = activities; orange sticky note = actors Green sticky note= positive influence; blue sticky note= neutral influence; pink sticky note= negative influence; green pen for product fluxes; red pen for services fluxes, blue pen for monetary fluxes).

4. Define the main actors who are part of the value chain. The names of the actors are written down on sticky notes and then placed on the map. The same process can then be done for supporting actors who are not directly linked to the value chain. At the beginning, it is not important where the actor cards are placed, what is more crucial is to collect as many potentially relevant actors.
5. Actors can then be rearranged on the map, according to the perception of the participants, using value chain activities as an orientation.
6. Once all the relevant actors are identified, the linkages connecting the various actors are drawn. Depending on the value chain, different categories of links may be relevant. Many value chain maps trace the flow of a product through the value chain and there is usually a flow of money going in the other direction. Other potentially relevant links could be information, sharing of technical knowledge, etc. No matter what the actual links are, they need to be clearly defined. Different links, e.g. information, money, etc., should be drawn with a different colored pen. Including a legend on the map can help the reader.

7. Complete the SWOT analysis form of the value chain to identify upgrading opportunities at the various nodes of the value chain (see Annex, section A2)
8. Complete the value chain upgrading opportunities form obtained from the weaknesses and threats identified in the SWOT analysis (Ewa-Belt Project, 2022) to identify the solutions to address those weaknesses and threats to upgrade the chain. (see Annex, section A2)
9. The last step is to validate the value chain map, asking participants if they agree, if they think the most relevant elements have been represented.

Points 7 and 8 can also be completed after the workshop using notes of recordings taken during the session.

After the exercise

After the exercise, results of the value chain mapping activity from each Living Lab (maps + supporting material) will be shared with UNIPI, after translation into English. The material will be shared via e-mail and, if necessary, accompanied by a video call to explain/provide additional information and feedback about the activity. Note that if you divide Living Lab participants into groups, multiple maps will be generated, that you will then have to elaborate yourselves or share with us. Lastly, free software (e.g. MindMaple <https://www.mindmaple.com>) can be used to report in English the map created during the Living Lab activity.

Table A.1. Needs and expectations template

NEEDS AND EXPECTATIONS FORM				
Country				
Region				
Partner				
Name and role dating	(their) Needs	(their) Expectations	(my) Needs	(my) Expectations
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				
7				
8				
...				

Table A.2. Example of a template used to carry out the SWOT analysis

SWOT ANALYSIS FORM				
Country	Finland			
Region	Uusimaa			
Partner	EFI			
Value chain activity				
SWOT component	Production	Aggregation	Trading	Processing
Strengths (what is working well)	Knowledge, the farmers have good knowledge of the system.			
	Production, the farmers are happy with the production system.			
	Agroecology, the farmers are happy that the production system is focussed on agroecology and this has created a more sustainable system, just like what they had in mind.			
	Economy, the farm is economically viable.			
	Supply of inputs is fine. Good connection with suppliers and maintenance network.			
				Good relations with customers
Weaknesses (what is not working well)			Lack of Marketing skills and lack of time to improve marketing.	
				No on-farm processing for a higher added value, no grain processing. Just sales of raw material. No time for hiring more personnel to for example improve on-farm processing.
Opportunities (incentives to grow)			Direct marketing	
	Seedling production			
	Advisory services			
Threats (obstacles to the business)		Climate change		
		War		
		Politics		

Table A.3. Template to capture the opportunities to upgrade the value chain

UPGRADING OPPORTUNITIES FORM				
Country				
Region				
Partner				
Value chain 1				
Product	Main Upgrading Opportunities (VC gaps/problems)	Rank in Order of Importance	Solution/Related New Technology	Rank in Order of Feasibility
Product 1				
Product 2				
Product 3				
Product 4				

References

- McBrown, J. (2021) What are facilitation skills and how do you facilitate?
<https://www.roffeypark.ac.uk/knowledge-and-learning-resources-hub/what-are-facilitation-skills-and-how-do-you-facilitate/>
- Kaplinsky, R., Morris, M. (2000) A Handbook for Value Chain Research. Brighton, UK: Institute of Development Studies. 106 pp
http://asiandrivers.open.ac.uk/documents/Value_chain_Handbook_RKMM_Nov_2001.pdf
- Stanford Graduate School of Education (2022) Bringing cooperative learning structures online using breakout room. <https://teachingresources.stanford.edu/resources/bringing-cooperative-learning-structures-online-using-breakout-rooms/>
- Stein, C., Barron, J. (2017) Mapping actors along value chains: integrating visual network research and participatory statistics into value chain analysis. Research for Development Learning Series 5. CGIAR Research Program on Water, Land and Ecosystems (WLE). 28 pp. doi: 10.5337/2017.216
https://www.iwmi.cgiar.org/Publications/wle/r4d/wle_research_for_development-learning_series-5.pdf
- Voinov, A., Jenni, K., Gray, S., Kolagani, N., Glynn, P.D., Bommel, P., Prell, C., Zellner, M., Paolisso, M., Jordan, R., Sterling, E., Schmitt Olabisi, L., Giabbanelli, P.J., Sun, Z., Le Page, C., Elsayah, S., BenDor, T.K., Hubacek, K., Laursens, B.K., Jetter, A., Basco-Carrera, L., Singer, A., Young, L., Jessica Brunacinic, Smajgl, A., (2018) Tools and methods in participatory modeling: Selecting the right tool for the job. Environmental Modelling and Software 109, 232–255.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2018.08.028>

APPENDIX B: Advances on the Blockchain technologies for Iberian dehesa products

Farmers in the Iberian pasture have been demanding for years a fair mechanism to be able to incorporate the values associated with their products into the market, values that can be summarized as quality, animal welfare and sustainability. In view of the complexity and density of information (or indicators) that is required to define these 3 values and the diversity of actors and consumers eventually involved, technologies such as blockchain are very well received by the sector.

An important advantage of the blockchain technology is the possibility of incorporating relevant information about the managed ecosystems, such as the value of emissions and/or capture of gases responsible for global warming at different stages. The adequate certification of this information can be useful, on the one hand, to raise funds in emerging environmental markets and, on the other, to transform the subsidy system into a system of payments for environmental services.

However, the implementation of this technology for the commercialization of any of the products of the Iberian pasture requires at least 3 premises:

- (i) Collective work in the sector, through associations of producers and with the rest of the actors in the value chain.
- (ii) Availability of reliable and practical protocols and indicators for the assessment of natural values, sustainability, and animal welfare on farms in the Iberian dehesa.
- (iii) Digitization of the sector, making it easier and more reliable to upload information of interest.

Bearing in mind these premises and the interest of blockchain for dehesa farmers, the operational groups SOSTVAN was created with the objective of designing and testing a blockchain for dehesa livestock products, taking the Spanish extensive beef as pilot product. It is important to highlight that 90% of suckler cows in Spain are found on extensive farms, both in dehesas and mountain pastures. The total area of permanent pastures in Spain is 8.3 million hectares, of which approximately 50% are habitats of community interest included in the Natura 2000 Network. In these areas, livestock activity has become an essential instrument for the protection of landscape resources and biodiversity, both through the direct influence of livestock and agroforestry practices.

SOSTVAN is integrated by multiple actors such as farmers, researchers, advisers and companies, with collaborations with environmental groups and consumer interest groups. Although this group only worked in a pilot project, the experience has guided the creation of two collaborative blockchains that are already working in the commercialization of dehesa livestock products: (i) Defhesa, a blockchain managed by multiple actors operating in the value chain of dehesa beef marketed his own mark; (ii) Iberchain, a blockchain created for the commercialization of pure Iberian pigs fattened in free-range dehesas.

In this report, we describe the SOSTVAN blockchain with some details and give a brief description of the other two, IBERCHAIN and Defhesa. We also give some reflections on the challenges that must be addressed to digitize a sector whose first actors (farmers) has taken few steps to incorporate new technologies, and on the difficulties for the commercial implementation of this technology by dehesa producers.

The blockchain in a nutshell

Blockchain technology acts as an immense accounting book, incorporating all the relevant information generated in the value chain, meeting three requirements: security, transparency and decentralization. Blockchain technology generates trust in the final consumer and develops a differentiation strategy of products.

It can be defined as a mathematical structure for storing data in a way that is almost impossible to fake. It is a public e-book that can be openly shared between disparate users and creates an immutable record of your transactions. Each digital record in the thread is called a block (hence the name), and allows an open or controlled group of users to participate in the e-book. In turn, each block is linked to a specific participant. Blockchain can only be updated by consensus among participants in the system, and when new data is entered, it can never be erased. There is a true and verifiable record of each and every entry made into the system.

The information contained in a blockchain exists as a shared, and continually reconciled, database. The blockchain database is not stored in a single location, which means that the records it keeps are truly public and easily verifiable. There is no centralized version of this information for a hacker to corrupt. Hosted by millions of computers simultaneously, data are accessible to anyone on the Internet.

Due to the open, decentralized, and cryptographic nature of blockchain technology, it is possible to (i) avoid intermediaries in transactions between untrusted parties; and (ii) generate an immutable ledger maintained by the network of nodes, which, through the use of a consensus algorithm, make the blockchain tamper-proof.

The SOTVAN blockchain

The SOSTVAN operational group is integrated by (i) UGAVAN, the association of extensive beef producers, (ii) Dehesa Grande, a cooperative of dehesa cattle farmers that own shared facilities for calve fattening and slaughter, (iii) Ibercom, a cooperative of Iberian livestock breed producers, (iv) DeHeus Animal Nutrition, a feed supplier; (v) MSD Animal Health, a company of veterinary services, (vi) the regional government of Castilla-León, (vii) MAB-UNESCO program, and (viii) three Universities (Extremadura (UEX), Salamanca (USAL) and León(ULE)).

Working together from 2021, SOSTVAN has designed a blockchain system in which all the data of interest for the traceability of the cattle product, from the birth of the animals to their slaughter, and the farm and meat processing companies are collected. A blockchain system based on Ethereum has been deployed to monitor feeding, prophylaxis practices, movements and animal welfare are recorded together with nature values and carbon footprint of the farms. In addition, an interactive and simple graphical interface has been designed allowing the user to manage, visualize and handle the data in a very intuitive way. Finally, traceability can be followed through an interface that takes advantage of the use of QR codes to make the most relevant data known to the end customer in a summarized and clear way. The functionality of these interfaces and their behavior are briefly described below. The description refers to eight items (Table B.1).

Table B.1 Eight items covered by the blockchain system

Animal records	Feed nutrition	Animal welfare
Slaughter stage	Farm nature values	Carbon footprint
Others data (transport, sales)	Traceability	

12.1 Choice of the database

It has been decided to use a documentary NoSQL database whose characteristics are ideal for storing data with these types of requirements. Among all the existing document databases in the current panorama, MongoDB was chosen. The choice was preceded by a prior study of its characteristics that make it flexible in the face of heterogeneous data structures, since there will be data from different sources and various partners, such as the different traceability actors, including feed suppliers or meat industry workers. In addition, synchronized data replication is allowed, which adds scalability to the project in case of large growth of the platform.

MongoDB has unique features such as the following:

- Flexible data model. It is a non-relational, collection-based database. The main advantage of collections is that they are variable and have no restrictions on their structure, so the schema can evolve over time.
- High scalability. The database structure is scalable both horizontally and vertically.
- Tools for deployment, monitoring and scaling of nodes quickly and efficiently.
- Query language with operators at the field level and for different types of data.

MongoDB uses the JSON format to store its data, specifically when storing these documents it uses the BSON format, a type of JSON in binary format. This format is mainly used to increase reading and writing efficiency.

Figure B.1. Characteristics of the MongoDB used in the SOSTVAN blockchain

Data model and security

Once the database was chosen, it was necessary to create the data model to maintain the traceability of the different elements of the system. These must include the storage of data from farms, slaughterhouses, feed manufacturers, external evaluators, as well as the elements that these entities manage such as feed and the cows themselves.

After knowing all the parameters that need to be stored, an extensible data model was created that includes the entities that participate in the traceability of livestock throughout the value chain and that allows new entities to be incorporated in case the project continues to grow (Figure B.2).

Figure B.2. Traceability system of the SOSTVAN blockchain

These data, which are of vital importance for the traceability of livestock, in some cases represent sensitive data for the integrity of the farm and must be protected to avoid information leaks.

On the one hand, the data is logically protected through a visibility system, which means that both when displaying it on the blockchain network and when storing this data to serve it on the platform, the visibility classify them as:

- Public. It can be seen by everyone.
- Semi-private. It can be seen by whoever enter it, members of the platform and end clients.
- Private. It can only be seen by whoever enters it.

On the other hand, the data shown above is protected against third-party attacks and is served through a secure layer thanks to a web service that prevents sensitive data from being obtained by

users who do not belong to the project. This is achieved by authenticating the calls using JWT (Json Web Token) technology, in which the user needs to authenticate themselves on the platform. Once the token is received, the calls made by the user to each of the methods that make up the platform's collections will be duly authenticated and, therefore, we will be avoiding privilege escalation attacks and access to sensitive information by unwanted third parties.

Animal records

This section allows adding new animals by filling out the form that appears or downloading a CSV template to register several animals at the same time. Mandatory data to register a new animal are (Figure B.3):

- Ear tag ID: Unique identifier of the animal.
- Animal breed: Type of breed of the animal.
- Date of birth: Date of birth of the animal.
- Sex of the animal: Indicate if the animal is male or female.
- Location of birth farm: This information is filled in automatically when a farm is selected from the list (previously farm must be registered by filling required fields with basic data).
- Location of the entity: Indicates the entity (farm, feedlot, slaughter) where the new animal is located within the existing list. If the entity is not found on the list, the entity must first be registered.

Rellene el formulario con los datos que se solicitan

ATRÁS NACIMIENTO SIGUIENTE

ID cinta Raza del animal

Fecha de nacimiento Macho Hembra

Elegir una localización Localización de la explotación de nacimiento - Este campo es obligatorio

Tipo de explotación de nacimiento Peso al nacer

Profilaxis en neonatos Nº de animales de edad similar

VOLVER REGISTRAR ANIMAL

Figure A.3. Basic data for the registration of new animals

After the registration of the animal, sections are available for the respective stages: birth, lactation and fattening.

Birth (Figure B.3) covers:

- Birth weight: The number of kilograms of the animal at birth.
- Prophylaxis at birth: Indicate the type of prophylaxis for the animal.
- Number of animals of similar age: Reflects how many animals exist at that moment with the similar age of the newborn.

Lactation (Figure B.4) covers:

- Location: Place of lactation of the animal.
- Farm code, location and type of exploitation (autocompleted).
- Type of farm: mountain wood pastures, mountain grasslands, dehesa, open pastures
- Food supplementation during lactation: Indicates if the animal is taking a food supplement during lactation.
- Weaning weight: Weight of the animal in kilograms (kg) at the time of weaning.
- Weaning age: Date on which the animal finished breastfeeding from the mother.
- Stocking rate during lactation: Relationship between the number of animals and the available grazing surface.
- Area covered during lactation: Indicates if the area is covered during the fattening process.
- Deworming during lactation: Procedure by which the parasites that the animal may harbour inside its body, between its fur or in breast milk are eliminated.
- Vaccination during lactation: Medications given to the animal to prevent basic diseases.
- Treatment during lactation: The type of treatment that the animal has followed during lactation.

Rellene el formulario con los datos que se solicitan

ATRÁS LACTANCIA SIGUIENTE

Elige una localización

Localización de la explotación durante lactancia - Este campo se autocompleta. Elige primero una localización

Tipo de explotación durante lactancia

Detalle explotación durante lactancia - Este campo se autocompleta. Elige primero una localización

Suplementación alimenticia durante lactancia

Peso al destete

Edad de destete

Carga ganadera durante lactancia

Puntuación encuesta Bienestar Animal

Certificación voluntaria Bienestar Animal

Zona cubierta durante lactancia

Desparasitación durante lactancia

Vacunación durante lactancia

Tratamiento durante lactancia

VOLVER REGISTRAR ANIMAL

Figure B.4. Data recording during lactation of the calves

Fattening (Figure B.5) covers:

- Location: Place where the animal is fattened.
- Farm location: Farm location where the animal is located during the fattening process.
- Feeding during fattening: Type of feeding that the animal receives during the fattening phase.
- Exploitation census (farm or feedlot): Indicates the exploitation census of the animal during fattening.
- Livestock load in feedlot: The relationship between the number of animals and the grazed surface available during the fattening process.
- Area covered during fattening: Indicates if the area is covered during the fattening process.

Rellene el formulario con los datos que se solicitan

ATRÁS ENGORDE SIGUIENTE

Elige una localización

Localización de la explotación durante engorde - Esta carga se auto-completará
Elige primero una localización

Alimentación durante el cebo

Censo explotación de cebo - Esta carga se auto-completará
Elige primero una localización

Puntuación encuesta Bienestar Animal

Certificación voluntaria Bienestar Animal

Carga ganadera en cebadero

Zona cubierta durante cebo

VOLVER REGISTRAR ANIMAL

Figure B.5. Data recording during lactation of the calves

Animal nutrition

To guarantee this traceability, the feed producers participating in the project are responsible for sending the order details to the platform each time a feed is unloaded on the farms belonging to the platform. These producers already have internal traceability processes. In this way, when they receive an order from a farm belonging to SOSTVAN, they invoke an API that stores in the database the most important elements of that order, such as the entity that has ordered that batch of feed, the type of feed downloaded and the specific batch that identifies that order.

Animal welfare

- Animal Welfare survey score: Assessment according to the Animal Welfare survey.
- Voluntary Animal Welfare Certification: If you have the official Animal Welfare certification given voluntarily.

Slaughter stage

Entities registered as slaughterhouses authorized for the slaughter of animals are responsible for notifying the platform that they have received a batch of animals at their facilities (Figure B.6). At that moment, the platform records the movement of these animals and their reception at the slaughterhouse with their corresponding recording parameters.

- Location: Place of sacrifice of the animal.
- Location of exploitation: Location of the exploitation where the animal is located during the slaughter process.
- Carcass weight: Weight of the animal once it has gone through the slaughter process.
- Date of slaughter: Date on which the animal is slaughtered.
- Sanitary location of the slaughterhouse: Place where the slaughter is carried out with the officially established sanitary measures.
- Cutting room location: Place where the animal is cut after slaughter.
- Slaughter order number: Number to identify the animal in the slaughter process.
- Slaughter classification: The type of classification that is determined for the animal at its sacrifice.

- Net weight: Weight of the animal without including the container or packaging.
- Gross weight: Weight of the animal including the container or packaging.
- Same owner of birth and fattening farm: Determines whether the place of birth farm coincides with the fattening farm.
- Belongs to the PGI: Protected Geographical Indication (PGI) determines whether the animal has a specific geographical origin.
- SEUROP Classification: Indicates whether it complies with the standardization and transparency of transactions related to beef in the European single market.

Figure B.6. Template for the recording data at the slaughterhouses

Farm nature values and carbon footprint

This component (Figure B.7) covers:

- GHG emission by surface: Figure captures greenhouse emissions based on the land surface.
- GHG emissions in transportation and processing: Indicates the value of greenhouse emissions in relation to the transportation and processing of products.
- Carbon footprint per surface: amount of direct gases that are emitted into the atmosphere.
- Carbon footprint per kg of meat: Carbon footprint of the product: Represents the net emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG) measured as CO₂e (CO₂ equivalent) of the animal.
- Carbon sequestration: An estimation of the annual rate of carbon sequestration in the soil and woody vegetation of the farm.
- Sustainable territorial management index: Index that summarizes indicators of environmental sustainability, equity, democratic governance, social and territorial cohesion.
- Potential biodiversity index: Index that summarizes indicators of forest planning and management, designed mainly to facilitate the integration of biodiversity conservation criteria in multifunctional management.
- Sustainable grazing index: Index that summarizes indicators of effective regenerative rotational grazing.

Figure B.7. Data regarding the nature value and carbon footprint of the farms

Others

- Client who brings the animals: Person/company responsible for bringing the animals.
- Type of channel: Sector management element, which improves the transparency of commercial transactions.
- Carrier (name and surname): Name and surname of the person in charge of transporting the vehicle.
- It belongs to the DG brand: If the animal is registered by the General Directorate (DG).
- Mother identifier: Unique identification number of the animal's mother.
- It has been slaughtered under the Halal rite: It guarantees whether the animal sacrifice process has been carried out under the rules of the Halal rite.
- Electronic identification of the animal: If it has an electronic registration identification.
- It is a fighting bull: Indicates if the animal is a bull from the fighting breed.
- Degree of fattening of the carcass (SEUROP): Refers to the importance of fat on the outside of the carcass and on the inside of the thoracic cavity according to SEUROP standards.
- Liver seal number: Identifier to indicate the part of the animal's liver.
- Number of months to slaughter: Indicates the number of months elapsed to slaughter.
- Complies with the conditions of the brand: Lists the different brands that guarantee the conditions of the animal product.

Traceability

To complete the traceability of the animals that adhere to the platform and their feeding, it is necessary to trace the processes that each cattle goes through at the time of transfer to slaughter. Through this method, the entity in charge of this process is able to obtain the QR code that will identify the final product that the customer will receive at the points of sale and distribution. When this process is finished, the result is a QR code that the customer can scan. Through this QR code, the client gains access to a traceability web portal, a visual and easy-to-understand way. This website has

several sections. First, a general table appears with information about the animal where parameters such as its breed or date of birth are specified, as can be seen in Figure B.8.

Figure B.8. View of the first block of basic information provided by the blockchain for the public consultation

Next, the website shows a series of animal welfare and basic farm environmental indicators provided by the organizations in charge of this surveillance, which reinforces the idea supported by the project that the processes carried out on the farms comply with all existing regulations, giving as result in a product of the best quality (Figure B.9). This also includes information about endangered breed, indicating that with our purchase we are contributing to the maintenance of that breed.

Figure B.9. View of the second and third public blocks of the blockchain with information about animal welfare and basic environmental values

Operating blockchains for Iberian dehesa products

Defhesa

Defhesa, the Spanish Sustainable Beef Association, is an association of companies and professionals in the beef sector, from all levels of the production chain (Fig B.10). The fundamental objective is promoting the sustainability of meat, promoting collaboration and mutual support between the different actors in the sector to align them with the UN SDGs, and by creating a Digital ecosystem to trace, audit and certify extensive beef products produce in sustainable grazing farms. With this aim, it has issued a blockchain certificate of traceability and quality of beef (<https://defhesa.org/plataforma-de-certificacion-basada-en-blockchain/>).

Defhesa is integrated by:

- Beef farmers: an open list of leading quality farms committed to the sustainability of the beef industry.
- Animal health companies and professionals.
- Animal food companies: Producers and manufacturers in the animal feed sector.
- Wholesalers and Distributors.
- Retailers and HORECA sector.
- Agri-food consulting: associated to Defhesa or collaborating in its projects by providing support, ideas, advice and technological solutions to the association and its members.
- Suppliers and Processors: Organizations that supply goods and services to beef producers or transform live cattle into a saleable product.
- Civil society: open collaboration with academic institutions, universities, non-governmental and non-commercial organizations, foundations and other types of associations that participate in some way in the beef value chain.

The digital ecosystem records all the activity of all user-operators, the relevant facts and interactions with the livestock on each farm, the transfers of livestock between operators and traces, audits and certifies the veracity of the process in an immutable way.

Figure B.10. View of the entry to Defhesa blockchain

To create value for associates and given that the blockchain allows important quality parameters to be certified, Defhesa has created 'De Dehesa' quality brand. With DE DEHESA label, three pillars are guaranteed: Animal welfare, Quality and Sustainability, with standards audited and certified by Global GAP (GGN Certified Livestock), with an impact on 12 of the 17 established Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the UN. GLOBALG.AP (Good Agricultural Practices) is a global quality and food safety standard that was created in 1997 and has more than 200,000 certified producers in the world. Not content with only certifying the origin of food and detecting the need to control the entire process up to the supermarket shelf, GLOBALG.AP created the GGN quality mark with the aim that the consumer could identify and purchase products with good practices of animal welfare and respect for the environment.

The consumer can check its origin in an online database through the individual registration number that appears on the label of each product and by accessing the site: livestock.ggn.org. The GGN brand, which certifies the product from the farm to the supermarket shelf and is already consolidated in aquaculture and floriculture, is implemented for the first time in livestock farming through Defhesa as a meat company (livestock farms, slaughterhouses and meat processing plants). The GGN livestock brand, granted by ARAPORCEI, a product certification entity accredited and authorized by GLOBALG.AP, certifies compliance with good practices in aspects such as animal health and well-being, worker well-being, the responsible use of antibiotics, food safety, product traceability and respect for the environment.

Iberchain

IBERCHAIN (<https://iberchain.es>) is integrated by 8 important cooperatives and companies producing Iberian pigs dehesas and commercializing their products: Aeceriber, Cedesa, Coveless, SanchezRomeroCarvajal, Ibercom, Renacens, Señoría de Montanera and Covap.

IBERCHAIN was born with the need to improve the traceability of meats and the implementation of a differentiated quality brand (100% native Iberian breed), through the Blockchain technology. The objective is to market the dehesa pig production through a quality differentiation with respect to other meats that abound in the market and that do not comply with the 100% Iberian breed purity. Data supply is based on the characterization of meat pieces measured automatically by NIRS technology that is able to capture parameters related with the animal genetic and nutrition (Figure B.11).

They use the blockchain to record transactions, processes or state changes of animals/products for which there is a need to certify a group of users in which said transition or state change has occurred. The technology used is called Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), because what this technology achieves is to create a type of notarial record (ledger) without the need for a central notarial authority. This is basically achieved by defining consensus rules and establishing verification rules for them when designing the blockchain.

Figure B.11. View of the entry to Ibercom blockchain

The challenge of digitalization in the beef sector

The digitization of the sector involves the need to be able to collect, process and manage large amounts of information from all participants in the value chain. As in other industries, it presents a significant challenge in terms of information security, as well as must guarantee the authenticity, integrity and confidentiality of data. At the same time, an information ecosystem must also be generated that favours verifiable transparency and collaboration between companies, while maintaining the confidentiality of business secrets.

Taking into account the previous observations, the digitalization process must first address the identification of the technology that must be implemented, as well as the best way to do it, to avoid a digital gap between the profile of the users and the training necessary for their implementation. The starting point of the beef value chain is in small, extensive livestock farms where, sometimes, the use of technology is less common than in other sectors that have already been digitalized. The characteristics of the operations mean that it is common to deal with professionals whose habitual use of technology is limited to the mobile phone and who, in many cases, do not use third-party applications (except for messaging) nor do they have computer knowledge, not even at the user level. Indeed, the SOSTVAN operational group has identified that the greatest difficulty for the implementation of blockchains in the sector is linked to capturing data on extensive livestock farms and uploading it to the platform. This has led us to look for solutions that companies like Deloitte have already developed and tested in analogous situations. For this reason, SOSTVAN is working with Deloitte for the implementation of the pilot blockchain above presented.

Deloitte has been working on the digitalization of processes for decades and have developed easy-to-use instruments for data capture, supported by technologies such as mobility, digital identity, artificial intelligence and blockchain. All of them wrapped in a user experience that allows any user to obtain the greatest potential from them, regardless of their level of technical knowledge. Furthermore, the implementation of the solutions does not end with their computer development, but it is necessary to support users in the management of change, training, monitoring and reinforcement to guarantee their correct adoption.

For Deloitte, a fundamental principle is to always keep in mind that one of the main activities of any exploitation is its own operation, and that data capture should not be - in any case - a process that makes said work difficult or slower. The great diversity of situations regarding the degree of modernization in farms is evident in the fact that we can find everything from the most traditional ones, which continue to carry out completely manual and paper-based management, to those that have specific computer programs in the farms. In between, there are usually farms that keep their management recorded in spreadsheets with various formats. The possible solutions that are currently available to respond to the following situations are explained below:

- Firstly, it is possible to take advantage of the data that all farms must record in the official records of each autonomous community, whether done by them or through agencies. This information constitutes a solid work base on which to build digitalization, without generating an additional minute of work for the farmers, and with the guarantee that the information is complete. Furthermore, for those farmers who additionally use spreadsheets or computer programs, information capture technologies allow the incorporation of specific sheets or program reports and contrasting the information with the existing information to guarantee integrity.
- On the other hand, the use of mobile technology is essential to be able to enrich the information, being able to digitize forms to be filled out from the mobile phone, as well as offering a way of interaction to add information or consult it through chatbots, in a manner analogous to when a user sends a message on WhatsApp or similar. It is also possible that users can provide photographs of documents, or animals, or phytosanitary products, etc. through their phones. To this we must add that, on many occasions, they have to deal with limited or no data coverage, which must allow the information to be captured at the moment and sent later, when a stable connection is available.
- Another way to simplify data capture and export is to take advantage of the Internet of Things (IoT) and connected devices that can provide information autonomously, without the farmer having to intervene, as is also the case with open data repositories.
- Furthermore, it must be kept in mind that the information recording needs evolve over time, and it is important that the capture system has flexibility, to be able to adapt to the requirements of each moment without impacting the user and always maintaining compatibility with all the existing information.
- Finally, the combined use of advanced digital identity technologies, electronic signature, artificial intelligence, electronic sealing, mobility, etc. has made it possible for these solutions to be working without hardly impacting the normal operations of users.

All these mechanisms are working successfully in Deloitte's OBA4Trace tool, a solution that allows to know step by step the stages that a product follows, from its origin to its consumption or disposal, through processing, storage, distribution and marketing. With this information is possible to efficiently control the supply chain, quickly report any incidents and the relationship with the end consumer and to show clearly and transparently the complete life cycle of the product.

In brief, the digitalization of the sector constitutes the cornerstone on which the improvement of the competitiveness of farms will be based (CAP O2), their positioning in the value chain (CAP) and guaranteeing quality and safety in the food chain (CAP O9). To achieve this development, it is

necessary to articulate procedures that, without taking time away from livestock farmers from their main activity, allow them to reach the advantages of the modern digital tools, such as the blockchain, to improve decision-making and better position themselves in the market.